

Chapter 1

Library Util

```
Require Export String.
Require Export List.
Require ClassicalEpsilon.
Require Classical.

Open Scope string_scope.
Open Scope list_scope.
Open Scope bool_scope.
```

1.1 A notation for lists

```
Notation "[ ]" := nil.
Notation "[ x ]" := (cons x nil).
Notation "[ x , .. , y ]" := (cons x .. (cons y nil) ..).
```

1.2 Conversion between Prop and *bool*

Definition *Trueb*(*P*: Prop): *bool* := if *ClassicalEpsilon.excluded_middle_informative P* then *true* else *false*.

Lemma *Trueb_true* (*P*: Prop): $P \leftrightarrow \text{Trueb } P = \text{true}$.

1.3 Properties of *Forall2*

Lemma *Forall2_implies_Forall2*{*X Y*}(*P Q*: $X \rightarrow Y \rightarrow \text{Prop}$):
 ($\forall x y, P x y \rightarrow Q x y$) \rightarrow
 $\forall xs ys,$
 Forall2 P xs ys \rightarrow
 Forall2 Q xs ys.

Lemma *Forall2_map1* {X1 X2 Y}(P: X2 → Y → Prop)(f: X1 → X2) xs ys:
Forall2 P (map f xs) ys ↔ *Forall2* (fun x y ⇒ P (f x) y) xs ys.

1.4 An overloaded decidable equality operator

```
Class EqDec(A: Type) := {
  eqb: A → A → bool;
  eqb_leibniz: ∀ x y, if eqb x y then x = y else x ≠ y
}.
```

Definition *eq_dec* {A} {eqa: EqDec A} (x y: A): {x = y} + {x ≠ y}.

Defined.

Definition *negb* {A} {eqa: EqDec A} (x y: A) := *negb* (eqb x y).

Infix "==" := *eqb* (at level 70).

Infix "!=" := *negb* (at level 70).

Definition *EqDec_of_eq_dec*{A}(eq_dec: ∀ (x y: A), {x = y} + {x ≠ y}): EqDec A.

Defined.

Instance *EqDec_string*: EqDec string := {eqb := fun x y ⇒ if string_dec x y then true else false}.

Defined.

Lemma *eqb_leibniz'* {A} {eqa: EqDec A} (x y: A):
 x == y = true → x = y.

Instance *EqDec_nat*: EqDec nat := {eqb := Nat.eqb}.

Defined.

Section *Forall2b*.

Context {A B}(p: A → B → bool).

```
Fixpoint forall2b(xs: list A)(ys: list B): bool :=
  match xs, ys with
  | [], [] ⇒ true
  | x::xs, y::ys ⇒ p x y && forall2b xs ys
  | -, - ⇒ false
end.
```

End *Forall2b*.

Lemma *forall2b_Forall2*{A B}(p: A → B → bool)(xs: list A)(ys: list B):
forall2b p xs ys = true →
Forall2 (fun x y ⇒ p x y = true) xs ys.

Lemma *forall2b_eqb_eq*{A}{eqa: EqDec A}(xs ys: list A):
forall2b eqb xs ys = true →
 xs = ys.

Instance *EqDec_list*{*A*}{*eqa*: *EqDec A*}: *EqDec (list A)* := {*eqb* := *forall2b eqb*}.
 Defined.

Instance *EqDec_pair*{*A B*}{*eqa*: *EqDec A*}{*eqb*: *EqDec B*}: *EqDec (A × B)* :=
 {*eqb* := *fun x y ⇒ (fst x == fst y) && (snd x == snd y)*}.
 Defined.

Instance *EqDec_bool*: *EqDec bool* := {*eqb* := *Bool.eqb*}.
 Defined.

Definition *mem* {*A*} {*eqa*: *EqDec A*} (*x*: *A*) (*xs*: *list A*): *bool* := *if in_dec eq_dec x xs*
then true else false.

Definition *contains*{*A*}{*eqa*: *EqDec A*}(*xs*: *list A*)(*x*: *A*): *bool* :=
existsb (fun x' ⇒ x' == x) xs.

Lemma *contains_in*{*A*}{*eqa*: *EqDec A*}(*xs*: *list A*)(*x*: *A*):
contains xs x = true ↔ In x xs.

Lemma *mem_eq_contains*{*A*}{*eqa*: *EqDec A*}(*xs*: *list A*)(*x*: *A*):
mem x xs = contains xs x.

Fixpoint *distinct*{*A*}{*eqa*: *EqDec A*}(*xs*: *list A*): *bool* :=
 match *xs* with
 || ⇒ *true*
 | *x::xs* ⇒ *negb (contains xs x) && distinct xs*
 end.

Lemma *distinct_map_eq*{*A B*}{*eqb*: *EqDec B*}(*f*: *A → B*)(*xs*: *list A*)(*x1 x2*: *A*):
distinct (map f xs) = true →
In x1 xs →
In x2 xs →
f x1 = f x2 →
x1 = x2.

Fixpoint *assoc*{*A B*}{*eqa*: *EqDec A*}(*default*: *B*)(*xys*: *list (A × B)*)(*x*: *A*): *B* :=
 match *xys* with
nil ⇒ *default*
 | (*x0*, *y0*)::*xys* ⇒ *if x0 == x then y0 else assoc default xys x*
 end.

Lemma *In_assoc* {*A B a0*} {*eqa*: *EqDec A*} {*xys*: *list (A × B)*} {*xys' a*}:
In a (map fst xys) →
assoc a0 (xys ++ xys') a = assoc a0 xys a.

Lemma *not_In_assoc* {*A B a0*} {*eqa*: *EqDec A*} {*xys*: *list (A × B)*} {*xys' a*}:
 ¬ *In a (map fst xys) →*
assoc a0 (xys ++ xys') a = assoc a0 xys' a.

Fixpoint *index_of*{*A*}{*eqa*: *EqDec A*}(*xs*: *list A*)(*x*: *A*): *nat* :=
 match *xs* with

```
|| => 0
| x0::xs0 => if x0 == x then 0 else S (index_of xs0 x)
end.
```

Chapter 2

Library Programs

Require Export *Util*.

Definition *cname* := *string*.

Definition *iname* := *string*.

Definition *var* := *string*.

Definition *fdn* := *string*.

Definition *gfdn* := *string*.

Definition *umname* := *string*.

Definition *mname*: **Type** := *cname* × *umname*.

Module Type *OTHER_TYPES*.

Parameter *other_type*: **Type**.

Parameter *other_type_eq_dec*: $\forall (ot1\ ot2: other_type), \{ot1 = ot2\} + \{ot1 \neq ot2\}$.

Parameter *other_value*: **Type**.

Parameter *other_value_welltyped*: *other_value* → *other_type* → **Prop**.

End *OTHER_TYPES*.

Module Types(*OtherTypes*: *OTHER_TYPES*).

Export *OtherTypes*.

Inductive *type* := *t_bool* | *t_void* | *t_in*(*I*: *iname*) | *t_cls*(*C*: *cname*)(*I*: *iname*) | *t_other*(*ot*: *other_type*).

Inductive *value* :=

v_bool(*b*: *bool*)

 | *v_unit*

 | *v_obj*(*C*: *cname*)(*fdvs*: *list* (*fdn* × *value*))(*I*: *iname*)(*gfdvs*: *list* (*gfdn* × *value*))

 | *v_other*(*vo*: *other_value*)

 .

Section *ObjWellTyped*.

Variable *obj_welltyped*: *value* → *type* → **Prop**.

```

Inductive value_welltyped0: value → type → Prop :=
| value_welltyped0_bool b:
  value_welltyped0 (v_bool b) t_bool
| value_welltyped0_unit:
  value_welltyped0 v_unit t_void
| value_welltyped0_in C fdvs I gfdvs:
  obj_welltyped (v_obj C fdvs I gfdvs) (t_in I) →
  value_welltyped0 (v_obj C fdvs I gfdvs) (t_in I)
| value_welltyped0_cls C fdvs I gfdvs:
  obj_welltyped (v_obj C fdvs I gfdvs) (t_cls C I) →
  value_welltyped0 (v_obj C fdvs I gfdvs) (t_cls C I)
| value_welltyped0_other ov ot:
  other_value_welltyped ov ot →
  value_welltyped0 (v_other ov) (t_other ot)
.

```

End *ObjWellTyped*.

End *Types*.

Definition *prec* := *mname* → *mname* → Prop.

Module Type *OPERATORS*(*OtherTypes*: *OTHER_TYPES*).

Module Export *TheTypes* := *Types OtherTypes*.

Parameter *operator*: Type.

Parameter *eq_dec_operator*: $\forall (op1\ op2: operator), \{op1 = op2\} + \{op1 \neq op2\}$.

Parameter *op_paramtypes*: *operator* → list *type*.

Parameter *op_resulttype*: *operator* → *type*.

Parameter *op_interp*: *prec* → *operator* → list *value* → *value*.

Parameter *op_interp_welltyped0*:

$\forall obj_welltyped\ pr\ op\ vs,$

$Forall2 (value_welltyped0\ obj_welltyped)\ vs\ (op_paramtypes\ op) \rightarrow$

$value_welltyped0\ obj_welltyped\ (op_interp\ pr\ op\ vs)\ (op_resulttype\ op).$

Parameter *level_lt*: *prec* → *value* → *value* → Prop.

Parameter *wf_level_lt*: $\forall pr: prec, well_founded\ pr \rightarrow well_founded (level_lt\ pr).$

End *OPERATORS*.

Module *Programs*(*OtherTypes*: *OTHER_TYPES*)(*Operators*: *OPERATORS OtherTypes*).

Export *Operators*.

Inductive *expr* :=

e_var(*x*: *var*)

| *e_op*(*op*: *operator*)(*es*: list *expr*)

| *e_fd*(*e*: *expr*)(*f*: *fdn*)

| *e_gfd*(*e*: *expr*)(*I*: *iname*)(*g*: *gfdn*)

```

| e_val(v: value).
Definition this := "this".
Definition result := "result".

Inductive cmd :=
  c_expr(e: expr)
| c_scall(C: cname)(m: umname)(args: list expr)
| c_icall(e: expr)(I: iname)(m: umname)(args: list expr)
| c_new(C: cname)(args: list expr)
| c_let(t: type)(x: var)(c c': cmd).

Inductive gfspec := GFSpec(t: type)(g: gfdn).
Inductive binding := Static | Instance.
Inductive mspec := MSpec(b: binding)(t: type)(m: umname)(params: list (type ×
var))(pre level post: expr).
Record itf := Itf {
  itfname: iname;
  itf_gfspecs: list gfspec;
  itf_mspeccs: list mspec
}.
Record cspec := CSpec {
  cspec_cname: cname;
  cspec_mspeccs: list mspec
}.
Inductive gf := GField(spec: gfspec)(e: expr).
Inductive method := Meth(spec: mspec)(c: cmd).
Record class := Class {
  clsname: cname;
  cls_fds: list (type × fdn);
  cls_itfs: list itf;
  cls_cspeccs: list cspec;
  cls_iname: iname;
  cls_gfs: list gf;
  clsmeths: list method
}.
Inductive program :=
  Program(itfs: list itf)(cs: list class).
Fixpoint gfspec_name(gfs: gfspec): gfdn :=
  match gfs with
  GFSpec t g => g
  end.
Fixpoint ms_name(meth: mspec): umname :=
  match meth with

```

```

    MSpec b t m xs P l Q ⇒ m
end.

Fixpoint meth_spec(meth: method): mspec :=
  match meth with
  | Meth ms c ⇒ ms
  end.

Fixpoint m_name(meth: method): umname :=
  match meth with
  | Meth (MSpec b t m xs P l Q) c ⇒ m
  end.

Fixpoint prog_itfs prog :=
  match prog with
  | Program itfs cls ⇒ itfs
  end.

Fixpoint prog_cls prog :=
  match prog with
  | Program itfs cls ⇒ cls
  end.

Fixpoint is_static(mspc: mspec): bool :=
  match mspc with
  | MSpec Static _ _ _ _ _ ⇒ true
  | _ ⇒ false
  end.

Fixpoint spec(cls: class): cspec :=
  match cls with
  | Class C fds itfs cspecs I_ gfs meths ⇒
  | CSpec C (flat_map (fun meth ⇒
    match meth with
    | Meth mspec _ ⇒ if is_static mspec then [mspec] else []
    end) meths)
  end.

Definition lookup_meth(ms: list method)(m: umname): option method :=
  find (fun meth ⇒ m_name meth == m) ms.

Definition lookup_mspec(mss: list mspec)(m: umname): option mspec :=
  find (fun ms ⇒ ms_name ms == m) mss.

Definition has_cspec(css: list cspec)(C: cname): bool := mem C (map cname css).

Definition lookup_cspec(css: list cspec)(C: cname): option cspec :=
  find (fun cs ⇒ cname cs == C) css.

Definition lookup_itf(itfs: list itf)(I: iname): option itf :=

```

find (fun itf \Rightarrow itfname itf == I) itfs.

Definition *lookup_class*(cls: list class)(C: cname): option class :=
find (fun cls \Rightarrow clsname cls == C) cls.

Lemma *cname_spec* cls: cname (spec cls) = clsname cls.

End *Programs*.

Chapter 3

Library ProgramExecution

Require Export *Programs*.

Require Export *Util*.

Module *ProgramExecution*(*OtherTypes*: *OTHER_TYPES*)(*Operators*: *OPERATORS OtherTypes*).

Include *Programs.Programs OtherTypes Operators*.

3.1 The program method precedence relation

This is relevant to program execution because the value of an operator expression may depend on the program method precedence relation.

```
Fixpoint list_prec {A} {eqa: EqDec A} (xs: list A) (x y: A): bool :=
  match xs with
  | nil => false
  | x0::xs0 => if x0 == x then mem y xs0 else list_prec xs0 x y
  end.
```

```
Fixpoint prog_clsprec_iter(n: nat)(clss: list class) C1 C2: bool :=
  match n with
  | 0 => false
  | S n =>
    match lookup_class clss C2 with
    | None => false
    | Some cls2 =>
      let css := cls_cspects cls2 in
      has_cspec css C1 ||
      existsb (fun cs => prog_clsprec_iter n clss C1 (cname cs)) css
    end
  end.
```

Definition *prog_clsprec*(*clss*: list class) := *prog_clsprec_iter* (length clss) clss.

Definition *prog_prec*(*prog*: *program*)(*Cm1 Cm2*: *mname*): *bool* :=
 let (*itfs*, *cls*) := *prog* in
 let (*C1*, *m1*) := *Cm1* in
 let (*C2*, *m2*) := *Cm2* in
 if *C1* == *C2* then
 match *lookup_class cls C1* with
 None ⇒ *false*
 | *Some cls* ⇒
list_prec (map m_name (clsmeths cls)) m1 m2
 end
 else
prog_clsprec cls C1 C2.

3.2 Substitution

Fixpoint *expr_subst*(*f*: *var* → *expr*)(*e*: *expr*): *expr* :=
 match *e* with
e_var x ⇒ *f x*
 | *e_op op es* ⇒ *e_op op (map (expr_subst f) es)*
 | *e_fd e fd* ⇒ *e_fd (expr_subst f e) fd*
 | *e_gfd e I_ g* ⇒ *e_gfd (expr_subst f e) I_ g*
 | *e_val v* ⇒ *e*
 end.

Definition *expr_subst_(xs: list var)(vs: list value): expr → expr* :=
expr_subst (fun x ⇒ e_val (assoc v_unit (combine xs vs) x)).

Definition *leave_var*(*x*: *var*)(*f*: *var* → *expr*)(*y*: *var*): *expr* :=
 if *y* == *x* then *e_var x* else *f y*.

Fixpoint *cmd_subst*(*f*: *var* → *expr*)(*c*: *cmd*): *cmd* :=
 match *c* with
c_expr e ⇒ *c_expr (expr_subst f e)*
 | *c_scall C m args* ⇒ *c_scall C m (map (expr_subst f) args)*
 | *c_icall e I_ m args* ⇒ *c_icall (expr_subst f e) I_ m (map (expr_subst f) args)*
 | *c_new C args* ⇒ *c_new C (map (expr_subst f) args)*
 | *c_let t x c c'* ⇒ *c_let t x (cmd_subst f c) (cmd_subst (leave_var x f) c')*
 end.

Definition *cmd_subst_(xs: list var)(vs: list value): cmd → cmd* :=
cmd_subst (fun x ⇒ e_val (assoc v_unit (combine xs vs) x)).

3.3 Evaluation and execution

Section *Program*.

Variable *prog*: *program*.

3.3.1 Expression evaluation

Section *Prec*.

Variable *pr*: *prec*.

```
Fixpoint eval(e: expr): value :=
  match e with
  | e_var x => v_unit
  | e_op op es => op_interp pr op (map eval es)
  | e_fd e f =>
    match eval e with
    | v_obj C fvs I gfvs => assoc v_unit fvs f
    | _ => v_unit
    end
  | e_gfd e I g =>
    match eval e with
    | v_obj C fvs I gfvs => assoc v_unit gfvs g
    | _ => v_unit
    end
  | e_val v => v
  end.
```

End *Prec*.

3.3.2 Command execution

Definition *eval_* := eval (fun *Cm1 Cm2* => *prog_prec prog Cm1 Cm2 = true*).

Inductive *outcome* := *terminates*(*result*: *value*) | *diverges*.

```
CoInductive exec: cmd → outcome → Prop :=
| exec_expr e: exec (c_expr e) (terminates (eval_ e))
| exec_scall C m args cls t xs P l Q c O:
  lookup_class (prog_cls prog) C = Some cls →
  lookup_meth (clsmeths cls) m = Some (Meth (MSpec Static t m xs P l Q) c) →
  exec (cmd_subst_ (map snd xs) (map eval_ args) c) O →
  exec (c_scall C m args) O
| exec_icall e m args C fvs I gfvs cls t xs P l Q c O:
  eval_ e = v_obj C fvs I gfvs →
```

```

lookup_class (prog_cls prog) C = Some cls →
lookup_meth (clsmeths cls) m = Some (Meth (MSpec Instance t m xs P l Q) c) →
exec (cmd_subst_ (this::map snd xs) (map eval_ (e::args)) c) O →
exec (c_icall e I m args) O
| exec_new C args fds itfs css I gfs ms:
lookup_class (prog_cls prog) C = Some (Class C fds itfs css I gfs ms) →
exec (c_new C args)
  (terminates
    (v_obj C
      (combine (map snd fds) (map eval_ args)) I
      (map
        (fun gf ⇒
          match gf with GField (GFSpec t g) e ⇒
            (g, eval_ (expr_subst_ (map snd fds) (map eval_ args) e))
          end)
        gfs)))
| exec_let_terminates t x c c' v O:
exec c (terminates v) →
exec (cmd_subst_ [x] [v] c') O →
exec (c_let t x c c') O
| exec_let_diverges t x c c':
exec c diverges →
exec (c_let t x c c') diverges
.

```

End Program.

End ProgramExecution.

Chapter 4

Library ProgramCorrectness

Require Export *ProgramExecution*.

Module *ProgramCorrectness*(*OtherTypes*: *OTHER_TYPES*)(*Operators*: *OPERATORS OtherTypes*).

Module Export *PE* := *ProgramExecution.ProgramExecution OtherTypes Operators*.

4.1 Correctness of commands and methods

Section *Ctxt*.

Variable *ctxt*: *class*.

Variable *pr*: *prec*.

Definition *eval e* := *eval pr e*.

4.1.1 Consistency of a value with respect to a type

Assumptions that can be made about the values of a type within the context of a single class (not knowing the rest of the program).

Inductive *consistent*: *value* → *type* → Prop :=

| *consistent_bool b*:

consistent (v_bool b) t_bool

| *consistent_unit*:

consistent v_unit t_void

| *consistent_itf C fds I gfds*:

 (∀ *gfss mss*,

lookup_itf (cls_itfs ctxt) I = Some (Itf I gfss mss) →

Forall2 gf_consistent gfds gfss) →

consistent (v_obj C fds I gfds) (t_in I)

| *consistent_cls C fds I gfds*:

 (∀ *gfss mss*,

```

    lookup_itf (cls_itfs ctxt) I = Some (Itf I gfss mss) →
    Forall2 gf_consistent gfds gfss) →
    consistent (v_obj C fds I gfds) (t_cls C I)
| consistent_other ov ot:
    other_value_welltyped ov ot →
    consistent (v_other ov) (t_other ot)
with gf_consistent: gfdn × value → gfspec → Prop :=
| gf_consistent_intro g v t:
    consistent v t →
    gf_consistent (g, v) (GFSpec t g)
.

```

4.1.2 Correctness of commands

Definition $v_true := v_bool\ true$.

```

Fixpoint instanceof(v: value)(I: iname): Prop :=
  match v with
  | v_obj _ _ I' _ => I' = I
  | _ => False
end.

```

Definition $eval' xs vs e := eval\ (expr_subst_xs\ vs\ e)$.

Definition $Psat xs vs P := eval' xs vs P = v_true$.

Definition $Qsat xs vs Q res := eval' (result::xs) (res::vs) Q = v_true$.

Inductive $correct(l: value): cmd \rightarrow (value \rightarrow Prop) \rightarrow Prop :=$

```

| correct_expr e Q:
  (Q (eval e): Prop) →
  correct l (c_expr e) Q
| correct_scall C m es cs t xs P el Q:
  lookup_cspec (spec ctxt::cls_cspecs ctxt) C = Some cs →
  lookup_mspecc (cspec_mspeccs cs) m = Some (MSpec Static t m xs P el Q) →
  Psat (map snd xs) (map eval es) P →
  level_lt pr (eval' (map snd xs) (map eval es) el) l →
  correct l (c_scall C m es) (Qsat (map snd xs) (map eval es) Q)
| correct_icall e m es I gfss mss t xs P el Q:
  instanceof (eval e) I →
  lookup_itf (cls_itfs ctxt) I = Some (Itf I gfss mss) →
  lookup_mspecc mss m = Some (MSpec Instance t m xs P el Q) →
  Psat (this::map snd xs) (map eval (e::es)) P →
  level_lt pr (eval' (this::map snd xs) (map eval (e::es)) el) l →
  correct l (c_icall e I m es) (Qsat (this::map snd xs) (map eval (e::es)) Q)
| correct_new C es Q fds itfs css I gfs ms:
  ctxt = Class C fds itfs css I gfs ms →

```

```

(Q (v_obj C (combine (map snd fds) (map eval es))) I
  (map
    (fun gf =>
      match gf with GField (GFSpec t g) e =>
        (g, eval' (map snd fds) (map eval es) e)
      end)
    gfs)): Prop) →
correct l (c_new C es) Q
| correct_let t x c c' Q R:
  correct l c Q →
  (∀ v, consistent v t → Q v → correct l (cmd_subst_ [x] [v] c') R) →
  correct l (c_let t x c c') R
| correct_conseq c Q Q':
  correct l c Q' →
  (∀ v, Q' v → Q v: Prop) →
  correct l c Q
.

```

4.1.3 Correctness of methods

```

Inductive field_consistent: fdn × value → type × fdn → Prop :=
| field_consistent_intro f v t:
  consistent v t →
  field_consistent (f, v) (t, f)
.

```

```

Inductive class_gf_consistent(eval: expr → value): gfdn × value → gf → Prop :=
| class_gf_consistent_intro g t e:
  class_gf_consistent eval (g, eval e) (GField (GFSpec t g) e)
.

```

```

Inductive instanceof_class: value → class → Prop :=
| instanceof_class_intro C fvs I gfs fds itfs css gfs ms:
  Forall2 field_consistent fvs fds →
  Forall2 (class_gf_consistent (eval' (map snd fds) (map snd fvs))) gfs gfs →
  instanceof_class (v_obj C fvs I gfs) (Class C fds itfs css I gfs ms)
.

```

```

Definition list_consistent(vs: list value)(ts: list type): Prop :=
  Forall2 consistent vs ts.

```

```

Inductive method_correct: method → Prop :=
| static_method_correct t m xs P el Q c:
  (∀ vs,
    list_consistent vs (map fst xs) →

```

```

    Psat (map snd xs) vs P →
    correct
      (eval' (map snd xs) vs el)
      (cmd_subst_ (map snd xs) vs c)
      (Qsat (map snd xs) vs Q)) →
    method_correct (Meth (MSpec Static t m xs P el Q) c)
| instance_method_correct t m xs P el Q c:
  (∀ o vs,
   instanceof_class o ctxt →
   list_consistent vs (map fst xs) →
   Psat (this::map snd xs) (o::vs) P →
   correct
     (eval' (this::map snd xs) (o::vs) el)
     (cmd_subst_ (this::map snd xs) (o::vs) c)
     (Qsat (this::map snd xs) (o::vs) Q)) →
   method_correct (Meth (MSpec Instance t m xs P el Q) c)
.
End Ctxt.

```

4.2 The class method precedence relation

```

Definition class_prec(cls: class)(Cm1 Cm2: mname): bool :=
  let (C1, m1) := Cm1 in
  let (C2, m2) := Cm2 in
  (C2 == clsname cls) &&
  (
    has_cspec (cls_cspects cls) C1
  ||
    (C1 == clsname cls) &&
    list_prec (map m_name (clsmeths cls)) m1 m2
  ).

```

4.3 Correctness of classes and programs

```

Inductive class_correct: class → Prop :=
| class_correct_intro cls:
  (∀ pr (Hwf_pr: well_founded pr),
   (∀ Cm1 Cm2, class_prec cls Cm1 Cm2 = true → pr Cm1 Cm2: Prop) →
   Forall (method_correct cls pr) (clsmeths cls)) →
  class_correct cls
.

```

```
Inductive program_correct: program → Prop :=
| program_correct_intro prog:
  Forall class_correct (prog_cls prog) →
  program_correct prog
.
End ProgramCorrectness.
```

Chapter 5

Library WellTyped

```
Require Export Util.
Require Export ProgramCorrectness.
Module WellTyped(OtherTypes: OTHER_TYPES)(Operators: OPERATORS OtherTypes).
Include ProgramCorrectness.ProgramCorrectness OtherTypes Operators.
```

5.1 Deciding equality of types

Definition *type_eq_dec*(*t1 t2*: type): {*t1 = t2*} + {*t1 ≠ t2*}.
Defined.

Definition *type_eqb* *t1 t2* := if *type_eq_dec* *t1 t2* then true else false.

Instance *EqDec_type*: EqDec type := {eqb := *type_eqb*}.
Defined.

5.2 Deciding equality of values

```
Fixpoint eqb_value(v1 v2: value): bool :=
  match v1, v2 with
  | v_bool b1, v_bool b2 => b1 == b2
  | v_unit, v_unit => true
  | v_obj C1 fvs1 I1 gfv1, v_obj C2 fvs2 I2 gfv2 =>
    (C1 == C2) &&
    (fix iter(fvs1 fvs2: list (fdn × value)): bool :=
      match fvs1, fvs2 with
      | [], [] => true
      | (f1, v1::fvs1, (f2, v2)::fvs2 => (f1 == f2) && eqb_value v1 v2 && iter fvs1 fvs2
      | -, - => false
      end) fvs1 fvs2 &&
```

```

(I1 == I2) &&
(fix iter(gfvs1 gfvs2: list (gfdn × value)): bool :=
  match gfvs1, gfvs2 with
    [], [] ⇒ true
  | (g1, v1)::gfvs1, (g2, v2)::gfvs2 ⇒ (g1 == g2) && eqb_value v1 v2 && iter gfvs1
gfvs2
  | -, - ⇒ false
  end) gfvs1 gfvs2
| v_other ov1, v_other ov2 ⇒ Trueb (ov1 = ov2)
| -, - ⇒ false
end.

```

```

Fixpoint eqb_fvs(fvs1 fvs2: list (string × value)): bool :=
  match fvs1, fvs2 with
    [], [] ⇒ true
  | (f1, v1)::fvs1, (f2, v2)::fvs2 ⇒ (f1 == f2) && eqb_value v1 v2 && eqb_fvs fvs1 fvs2
  | -, - ⇒ false
  end.

```

```

Definition eqb_value'(v1 v2: value): bool :=
  match v1, v2 with
    v_bool b1, v_bool b2 ⇒ b1 == b2
  | v_unit, v_unit ⇒ true
  | v_obj C1 fvs1 I1 gfvs1, v_obj C2 fvs2 I2 gfvs2 ⇒
    (C1 == C2) &&
    eqb_fvs fvs1 fvs2 &&
    (I1 == I2) &&
    eqb_fvs gfvs1 gfvs2
  | v_other ov1, v_other ov2 ⇒ Trueb (ov1 = ov2)
  | -, - ⇒ false
  end.

```

Lemma eqb_value_eq_eqb_value'(v1 v2: value): eqb_value v1 v2 = eqb_value' v1 v2.

```

Definition value_ind
  (P: value → Prop)
  (Pvs: list (string × value) → Prop)
  (Hnil: Pvs nil)
  (Hcons: ∀ f v fvs, P v → Pvs fvs → Pvs ((f, v)::fvs))
  (Hv_bool: ∀ b, P (v_bool b))
  (Hv_unit: P v_unit)
  (Hv_obj: ∀ C fvs I gfvs, Pvs fvs → Pvs gfvs → P (v_obj C fvs I gfvs))
  (Hv_other: ∀ ov, P (v_other ov)) :=
  fix iter(v: value): P v :=
  match v with

```

```

    v_bool b ⇒ Hv_bool b
  | v_unit ⇒ Hv_unit
  | v_obj C fvs L_ gfvs ⇒
    Hv_obj C fvs L_ gfvs
    ((fix iter'(fvs: list (string × value)): Pvs fvs :=
      match fvs with
      [] ⇒ Hnil
      | (f, v)::fvs ⇒ Hcons f v fvs (iter v) (iter' fvs)
      end) fvs)
    ((fix iter'(gfvs: list (string × value)): Pvs gfvs :=
      match gfvs with
      [] ⇒ Hnil
      | (g, v)::gvs ⇒ Hcons g v gvs (iter v) (iter' gvs)
      end) gfvs)
  | v_other ov ⇒ Hv_other ov
end.

```

Instance *EqDec_value*: *EqDec value* := {eqb := eqb_value}.
 Defined.

5.3 Deciding equality of expressions

Instance *EqDec_operator*: *EqDec operator* := {eqb := fun op1 op2 ⇒ if eq_dec_operator op1 op2 then true else false}.
 Defined.

```

Fixpoint eqb_expr(e1 e2: expr): bool :=
  match e1, e2 with
  e_var x1, e_var x2 ⇒ x1 == x2
  | e_op op1 es1, e_op op2 es2 ⇒
    (op1 == op2) &&
    (fix iter(es1 es2: list expr): bool :=
      match es1, es2 with
      [], [] ⇒ true
      | e1::es1, e2::es2 ⇒ eqb_expr e1 e2 && iter es1 es2
      | -, _ ⇒ false
      end) es1 es2
  | e_fd e1 f1, e_fd e2 f2 ⇒ eqb_expr e1 e2 && (f1 == f2)
  | e_gfd e1 I1 g1, e_gfd e2 I2 g2 ⇒ eqb_expr e1 e2 && (I1 == I2) && (g1 == g2)
  | e_val v1, e_val v2 ⇒ v1 == v2
  | -, _ ⇒ false
end.

```

Definition *expr_ind*

```

(P: expr → Prop)
(Pes: list expr → Prop)
(Hnil: Pes [])
(Hcons: ∀ e es, P e → Pes es → Pes (e::es))
(He_var: ∀ x, P (e_var x))
(He_op: ∀ op es, Pes es → P (e_op op es))
(He_fd: ∀ e f, P e → P (e_fd e f))
(He_gfd: ∀ e I g, P e → P (e_gfd e I g))
(He_val: ∀ v, P (e_val v)): ∀ e, P e :=
fix iter(e: expr): P e :=
match e with
  e_var x ⇒ He_var x
| e_op op es ⇒
  He_op op es
  ((fix iter'(es: list expr): Pes es :=
    match es with
      [] ⇒ Hnil
    | e::es ⇒ Hcons e es (iter e) (iter' es)
    end) es)
| e_fd e f ⇒ He_fd e f (iter e)
| e_gfd e I g ⇒ He_gfd e I g (iter e)
| e_val v ⇒ He_val v
end.

```

```

Fixpoint eqb_exprs(es1 es2: list expr): bool :=
match es1, es2 with
  [], [] ⇒ true
| e1::es1, e2::es2 ⇒ eqb_expr e1 e2 && eqb_exprs es1 es2
| -, - ⇒ false
end.

```

```

Definition eqb_expr'(e1 e2: expr): bool :=
match e1, e2 with
  e_var x1, e_var x2 ⇒ x1 == x2
| e_op op1 es1, e_op op2 es2 ⇒
  (op1 == op2) &&
  eqb_exprs es1 es2
| e_fd e1 f1, e_fd e2 f2 ⇒ eqb_expr e1 e2 && (f1 == f2)
| e_gfd e1 I1 g1, e_gfd e2 I2 g2 ⇒ eqb_expr e1 e2 && (I1 == I2) && (g1 == g2)
| e_val v1, e_val v2 ⇒ v1 == v2
| -, - ⇒ false
end.

```

```

Lemma eqb_expr_eq_eqb_expr'(e1 e2: expr): eqb_expr e1 e2 = eqb_expr' e1 e2.

```

Instance *EqDec_expr*: *EqDec expr := {eqb := eqb_expr'}*.
 Defined.

5.4 Deciding equality of specifications

Definition *eq_dec_binding*(*b1 b2: binding*): *{b1 = b2} + {b1 ≠ b2}*.
 Defined.

Instance *EqDec_binding*: *EqDec binding := EqDec_of_eq_dec eq_dec_binding*.

Definition *eq_dec_mspe*(*m1 m2: mspec*): *{m1 = m2} + {m1 ≠ m2}*.
 Defined.

Instance *EqDec_mspe*: *EqDec mspec := EqDec_of_eq_dec eq_dec_mspe*.

Definition *eq_dec_gfspe*(*gfs1 gfs2: gfspec*): *{gfs1 = gfs2} + {gfs1 ≠ gfs2}*.
 Defined.

Instance *EqDec_gfspe*: *EqDec gfspec := EqDec_of_eq_dec eq_dec_gfspe*.

Definition *eq_dec_itf*(*itf1 itf2: itf*): *{itf1 = itf2} + {itf1 ≠ itf2}*.
 Defined.

Instance *EqDec_itf*: *EqDec itf := EqDec_of_eq_dec eq_dec_itf*.

Definition *eq_dec_cspe*(*cs1 cs2: cspec*): *{cs1 = cs2} + {cs1 ≠ cs2}*.
 Defined.

Instance *EqDec_cspe*: *EqDec cspec := EqDec_of_eq_dec eq_dec_cspe*.

5.5 Well-typedness of expressions, commands, and types

Fixpoint *is_subtype*(*t1 t2: type*): *bool :=*
 match *t1, t2* with
 | *t_cls _ I1, t_in I2* ⇒ *I1 == I2*
 | *_, _* ⇒ *t1 == t2*
 end.

Fixpoint *expr_welltyped*(*value_welltyped: value → type → bool*)(*itfs: list itf*)(*cls: option class*)(*env: list (var × type)*)(*e: expr*)(*t: type*) {**struct** *e*}: *bool :=*
 match *e* with
 | *e_var x* ⇒ *is_subtype (assoc t_void env x) t*
 | *e_op op es* ⇒
 (fix *iter*(*es: list expr*)(*ts: list type*) {**struct** *es*}: *bool :=*
 match *es, ts* with
 | *[]*, *[]* ⇒ *true*
 | *e::es, t::ts* ⇒ *expr_welltyped value_welltyped itfs cls env e t && iter es ts*
 | *_, _* ⇒ *false*

```

    end) es (op_paramtypes op) && is_subtype (op_resulttype op) t
| e_fd e f ⇒
  match cls with
  | None ⇒ false
  | Some cls ⇒
    expr_welltyped value_welltyped itfs (Some cls) env e (t_cls (clsname cls) (cls_iname
cls)) &&
    is_subtype (assoc t_void (map (fun fd ⇒ match fd with (t, f) ⇒ (f, t) end) (cls_fds
cls)) f) t
  end
| e_gfd e I_ g ⇒
  expr_welltyped value_welltyped itfs cls env e (t_in I_) &&
  match lookup_itf itfs I_ with
  | None ⇒ false
  | Some (Itf _ gfs _) ⇒
    is_subtype (assoc t_void (map (fun gfs ⇒ match gfs with GFSpec t g ⇒ (g, t) end)
gfs) g) t
  end
| e_val v ⇒ value_welltyped v t
end.

```

Fixpoint *cmd_welltyped*(*value_welltyped*: *value* → *type* → *bool*)(*cls*: *class*)(*env*: *list* (*var* × *type*))(*c*: *cmd*)(*t*: *type*): *bool* :=

```

let expr_wt := expr_welltyped value_welltyped (cls_itfs cls) (Some cls) env in
match c with
| c_expr e ⇒ expr_wt e t
| c_scall C m args ⇒
  match lookup_cspec (spec cls::cls_cspects cls) C with
  | None ⇒ false
  | Some cs ⇒
    match lookup_mspec (cspec_mspects cs) m with
    | Some (MSpec Static t' - xs - -) ⇒
      forall2b expr_wt args (map fst xs) && is_subtype t' t
    | _ ⇒ false
    end
  end
| c_icall e I_ m args ⇒
  expr_wt e (t_in I_) &&
  match lookup_itf (cls_itfs cls) I_ with
  | None ⇒ false
  | Some (Itf _ - mss) ⇒
    match lookup_mspec mss m with
    | Some (MSpec Instance t' - xs - -) ⇒

```

```

    forall2b expr_wt args (map fst xs) && is_subtype t' t
  | _ => false
end
end
| c_new C args =>
  (C == clsname cls) &&
  forall2b expr_wt args (map fst (cls_fds cls)) &&
  is_subtype (t_cls C (cls_iname cls)) t
| c_let t' x c c' =>
  cmd_welltyped value_welltyped cls env c t' &&
  cmd_welltyped value_welltyped cls ((x, t')::env) c' t
end.

```

```

Fixpoint type_welltyped(Is: list iname)(t: type): bool :=
  match t with
    t_cls _ _ => false
  | t_in I_ => contains Is I_
  | _ => true
end.

```

5.6 Well-typedness of interfaces, classes, and programs

Section *TLevel*.

Variable *t_level*: *type*.

5.6.1 Well-typedness of interfaces and classes

```

Fixpoint mspec_welltyped(itfs: list itf)(I: option iname)(ms: mspec): bool :=
  match ms with
    MSpec b t m xs P el Q =>
      type_welltyped (map itfname itfs) t &&
      forallb (type_welltyped (map itfname itfs)) (map fst xs) &&
      distinct (map snd xs) &&
      match b, I with Instance, None => false | _, _ => true end &&
      let prefix :=
        match b, I with
          | Instance, Some I_ => [(this, t_in I_)]
          | -, - => []
        end
      in
      let env := prefix ++ map (fun tx: type × var => let (t, x) := tx in (x, t)) xs in
      let expr_wt := expr_welltyped (fun _ => false) itfs None in

```

```

    expr_wt env P t_bool &&
    expr_wt env el t_level &&
    expr_wt ((result, t)::env) Q t_bool
end.

Fixpoint itf_welltyped(itfs: list itf)(itf: itf): bool :=
  match itf with
  | Itf I_ gfss mss =>
    distinct (map (fun gfs => match gfs with GFSpec t g => g end) gfss) &&
    forallb (fun gfs => match gfs with GFSpec t g => type_welltyped (map itfname itfs) t
end) gfss &&
    distinct (map (fun ms => match ms with MSpec _ _ m _ _ _ => m end) mss) &&
    forallb (fun ms => negb (is_static ms)) mss &&
    forallb (mspec_welltyped itfs (Some I_)) mss
  end.

Fixpoint cspec_welltyped(itfs: list itf)(cs: cspec) {struct cs}: bool :=
  match cs with
  | CSpec C mss =>
    distinct (map ms_name mss) &&
    forallb (mspec_welltyped itfs None) mss
  end.

Fixpoint cls_welltyped(cls: class): bool :=
  match cls with
  | Class C fds itfs css I_ gfs ms =>
    distinct (map itfname itfs) &&
    forallb (itf_welltyped itfs) itfs &&
    distinct (C::map cname css) &&
    forallb (cspec_welltyped itfs) (spec cls::css) &&
    distinct (map snd fds) &&
    forallb (type_welltyped (map itfname itfs)) (map fst fds) &&
    distinct (map m_name ms) &&
    match lookup_itf itfs I_ with
    | None => false
    | Some (Itf _ gfss mss) =>
      (map (fun gf => match gf with GField gfs e => gfs end) gfs == gfss) &&
      (filter (fun ms => negb (is_static ms)) (map meth_spec ms) == mss) &&
      let gfenv := map (fun fd => (snd fd, fst fd)) fds in
      forallb (fun gf => match gf with GField (GFSpec t g) e => expr_welltyped (fun _ _
=> false) itfs None gfenv e t end) gfs &&
      forallb (fun meth => match meth with Meth (MSpec b t m xs P el Q) c =>
        let prefix :=
          match b with
          | Static => []

```

```

      | Instance  $\Rightarrow$  [(this, t_cls C I)]
    end
  in
  let env := prefix ++ map (fun tx  $\Rightarrow$  (snd tx, fst tx)) xs in
  cmd_welltyped (fun _ _  $\Rightarrow$  false) cls env c t
end) ms
end
end.

```

5.6.2 Satisfaction of class imports in a program

Each class' imports must be satisfied by earlier classes in the program.

```

Fixpoint class_imports_sat(itfs: list itf)(css: list cspec)(clss: list class): bool :=
  match clss with
  | []  $\Rightarrow$  true
  | cls::clss  $\Rightarrow$ 
    forallb (contains itfs) (cls_itfs cls) &&
    forallb (contains css) (cls_cspects cls) &&
    class_imports_sat itfs (spec cls::css) clss
  end.

```

5.6.3 An alternative characterization of satisfaction of class imports

Here, each class' imports must be satisfied by later classes in the program.

```

Fixpoint class_imports_sat'(itfs: list itf)(clss: list class): bool :=
  match clss with
  | []  $\Rightarrow$  true
  | cls::clss  $\Rightarrow$ 
    forallb (contains itfs) (cls_itfs cls) &&
    forallb (contains (map spec clss)) (cls_cspects cls) &&
    class_imports_sat' itfs clss
  end.

```

Lemma *class_imports_sat'_equiv_lemma* *itfs* *clss0* *clss1* *clss2*:

```

class_imports_sat itfs (map spec clss0) (clss1 ++ clss2) && class_imports_sat' itfs clss0 =
class_imports_sat itfs (map spec (rev clss1) ++ map spec clss0) clss2 &&
class_imports_sat' itfs (rev clss1 ++ clss0).

```

Lemma *class_imports_sat'_equiv* *itfs* *clss*:

```

class_imports_sat itfs [] (rev clss) = class_imports_sat' itfs clss.

```

5.6.4 Well-typedness of programs

```

Fixpoint program_welltyped(prog: program): bool :=

```

```
match prog with
  Program itfs cls =>
    distinct (map itfname itfs) &&
    distinct (map clsname cls) &&
    forallb (itf_welltyped itfs) itfs &&
    forallb cls_welltyped cls &&
    cls_imports_sat itfs [] cls
end.
End TLevel.
End WellTyped.
```

Chapter 6

Library Soundness

Require Export *ProgramCorrectness*.

Require Export *WellTyped*.

Require Import *Classical*.

Require Import *Omega*.

Module *Soundness*(*OtherTypes*: *OTHER_TYPES*)(*Operators*: *OPERATORS OtherTypes*).

Module Export *WT* := *WellTyped.WellTyped OtherTypes Operators*.

Section *Prog*.

Variable *t_level*: *type*.

Definition *program_welltyped*(*prog*: *program*): Prop := *program_welltyped t_level prog = true*.

Variable *prog*: *program*.

Variable *prog_welltyped*: *program_welltyped prog*.

Variable *prog_correct*: *program_correct prog*.

Definition *pr Cm1 Cm2* := *prog_prec prog Cm1 Cm2 = true*.

6.1 Well-typedness of values

Inductive *value_welltyped*: *value* → *type* → Prop :=

| *value_welltyped_bool* *b*:

value_welltyped (v_bool b) t_bool

| *value_welltyped_unit*:

value_welltyped v_unit t_void

| *value_welltyped_cls* *fdvs gfdvs C fds itfs css I gfs ms*:

In (Class C fds itfs css I gfs ms) (prog_cls prog) →

field_values_welltyped fdvs fds →

ghost_field_values_welltyped fdvs gfdvs gfs →

value_welltyped (v_obj C fdvs I gfdvs) (t_cls C I)

```

| value_welltyped_in fdvs gfdvs C fds itfs css I gfs ms:
  In (Class C fds itfs css I gfs ms) (prog_class prog) →
  field_values_welltyped fdvs fds →
  ghost_field_values_welltyped fdvs gfdvs gfs →
  value_welltyped (v_obj C fdvs I gfdvs) (t_in I)
| value_welltyped_other ov ot:
  other_value_welltyped ov ot →
  value_welltyped (v_other ov) (t_other ot)
with field_values_welltyped: list (fdn × value) → list (type × fdn) → Prop :=
| field_values_welltyped_nil:
  field_values_welltyped nil nil
| field_values_welltyped_cons f v t fdvs fds:
  value_welltyped v t →
  field_values_welltyped fdvs fds →
  field_values_welltyped ((f, v)::fdvs) ((t, f)::fds)
with ghost_field_values_welltyped: list (fdn × value) → list (gfdn × value) → list gf →
Prop :=
| ghost_field_values_welltyped_nil fdvs:
  ghost_field_values_welltyped fdvs nil nil
| ghost_field_values_welltyped_cons fdvs g v t e gfs gfs:
  value_welltyped v t →
  v = eval_prog (expr_subst (fun x ⇒ e_val (assoc v_unit fdvs x)) e) →
  ghost_field_values_welltyped fdvs gfs gfs →
  ghost_field_values_welltyped fdvs ((g, v)::gfs) (GField (GFSpec t g) e::gfs)
.

```

Scheme Induction for *value_welltyped* Sort Prop
with Induction for *field_values_welltyped* Sort Prop
with Induction for *ghost_field_values_welltyped* Sort Prop.

6.2 Consequences of well-typedness of the program

Lemma *cls_specs_subset_lemma* itfs css cls cs cs:
cls_imports_sat itfs css cls = true →
In cls cls →
In cs (cls_specs cls) →
In cs css ∨ In cs (map spec cls).

Lemma *cls_specs_subset* cls cs:
In cls (prog_class prog) →
In cs (cls_specs cls) →
In cs (map spec (prog_class prog)).

Lemma *cls_itfs_subset_lemma* itfs css cls cls itf:

cls_imports_sat itfs cls = true →

In cls cls →

In itf (cls_itfs cls) →

In itf itfs.

Lemma *cls_itfs_subset cls itf*:

In cls (prog_cls prog) →

In itf (cls_itfs cls) →

In itf (prog_itfs prog).

Lemma *distinct_itfname*:

distinct (map itfname (prog_itfs prog)) = true.

Lemma *distinct_clsname*:

distinct (map clsname (prog_cls prog)) = true.

Lemma *itfs_welltyped itf*:

In itf (prog_itfs prog) →

itf_welltyped t_level (prog_itfs prog) itf = true.

Lemma *cls_welltyped {P: Prop} cls*:

In cls (prog_cls prog) →

(distinct (map itfname (cls_itfs cls)) = true →

(∀ itf, In itf (cls_itfs cls) → itf_welltyped t_level (cls_itfs cls) itf = true) →

distinct (clsname cls::map cname (cls_specs cls)) = true →

cspec_welltyped t_level (cls_itfs cls) (spec cls) = true →

(∀ cs, In cs (cls_specs cls) → cspec_welltyped t_level (cls_itfs cls) cs = true) →

distinct (map snd (cls_fds cls)) = true →

(∀ t, In t (map fst (cls_fds cls)) → type_welltyped (map itfname (cls_itfs cls)) t = true)

→

distinct (map m_name (clsmeths cls)) = true →

∀ itf gfenv,

In itf (cls_itfs cls) →

itfname itf = cls_iname cls →

map (fun gf ⇒ match gf with GField gfs e ⇒ gfs end) (cls_gfs cls) = itf_gfspecs itf →

filter (fun ms ⇒ negb (is_static ms)) (map meth_spec (clsmeths cls)) = itf_msspecs itf

→

gfenv = map (fun fd ⇒ (snd fd, fst fd)) (cls_fds cls) →

(∀ gf, In gf (cls_gfs cls) → match gf with GField (GFSpec t g) e ⇒ expr_welltyped (fun

- - ⇒ false) (cls_itfs cls) None gfenv e t end = true) →

(∀ meth, In meth (clsmeths cls) →

match meth with Meth (MSpec b t m xs P el Q) c ⇒

let prefix :=

match b with

Static ⇒ []

| Instance ⇒ [(this, t_cls (clsname cls) (cls_iname cls))]

```

    end
  in
    let env := prefix ++ map (fun tx => (snd tx, fst tx)) xs in
      cmd_welltyped (fun _ => false) cls env c t
    end = true) →
  P) →
P.

```

Lemma prog_cls_distinct *cls1 cls2*:

```

  In cls1 (prog_cls prog) →
  In cls2 (prog_cls prog) →
  clsname cls2 = clsname cls1 →
  cls2 = cls1.

```

Lemma meth_mspec_distinct *cls ms ms' c*:

```

  In cls (prog_cls prog) →
  In ms (cspec_msspecs (spec cls)) →
  In (Meth ms' c) (clsmeths cls) →
  is_static ms' = true →
  ms_name ms = ms_name ms' →
  ms = ms'.

```

Lemma gfs_gfspecs *{C fds itfs css I gfs ms gfspecs mspecs}*:

```

  In (Class C fds itfs css I gfs ms) (prog_cls prog) →
  In (Itf I gfspecs mspecs) (prog_itfs prog) →
  gfspecs = map (fun gf: gf => let (gfs, e) := gf in gfs) gfs.

```

Lemma In_cls_itfs *itf cls*:

```

  In cls (prog_cls prog) →
  In itf (cls_itfs cls) →
  In itf (prog_itfs prog).

```

Lemma distinct_clsmeths *cls*:

```

  In cls (prog_cls prog) →
  distinct (map m_name (clsmeths cls)) = true.

```

Lemma static_method_body_welltyped *cls t m xs P l Q c*:

```

  In cls (prog_cls prog) →
  In (Meth (MSpec Static t m xs P l Q) c) (clsmeths cls) →
  cmd_welltyped (fun _ => false) cls (map (fun tx => (snd tx, fst tx)) xs) c t = true.

```

Lemma instance_method_body_welltyped *cls t m xs P l Q c*:

```

  In cls (prog_cls prog) →
  In (Meth (MSpec Instance t m xs P l Q) c) (clsmeths cls) →
  cmd_welltyped (fun _ => false) cls (map (fun tx => (snd tx, fst tx)) ((t_cls (clsname
cls) (cls_iname cls), this) :: xs)) c t = true.

```

Lemma class_implements_interface_methods *{I gfs mss C fds itfs css gfs ms}*:

In (Itf I gfs mss) (prog_itfs prog) →
In (Class C fds itfs css I gfs ms) (prog_cls prog) →
mss = filter (fun ms ⇒ negb (is_static ms)) (map meth_spec ms).

Lemma *ms_distinct ms m spec c:*

lookup_meth ms m = Some (Meth spec c) →

is_static spec = false →

lookup_ms_spec (filter (fun ms ⇒ negb (is_static ms)) (map meth_spec ms)) m = Some spec.

6.3 Properties of well-typedness of values

Lemma *value_welltyped_consistent cls v t:*

In cls (prog_cls prog) →

value_welltyped v t →

consistent cls v t.

Definition *value_welltypedb v t := Trueb (value_welltyped v t).*

Lemma *field_values_welltyped_assoc fdvs fds f:*

field_values_welltyped fdvs fds →

value_welltyped (assoc v_unit fdvs f) (assoc t_void (map (fun fd: type × fdn ⇒ let (t, f) := fd in (f, t)) fds) f).

Lemma *ghost_field_values_welltyped_assoc g: ∀ fdvs gfdvs gfs,*

ghost_field_values_welltyped fdvs gfdvs gfs →

value_welltyped (assoc v_unit gfdvs g)

(assoc t_void

(map (fun gfs: gfspec ⇒ match gfs with GFSpec t g ⇒ (g, t) end)

(map (fun gf: gf ⇒ let (gfs, e) := gf in gfs) gfs)) g).

Lemma *value_welltyped_subtype v t t0:*

is_subtype t t0 = true →

value_welltyped v t →

value_welltyped v t0.

Lemma *value_welltyped0_value_welltyped v t:*

value_welltyped0 value_welltyped v t → value_welltyped v t.

Lemma *value_welltyped_value_welltyped0 v t:*

value_welltyped v t → value_welltyped0 value_welltyped v t.

Lemma *value_welltyped_op_interp prec op vs:*

forall2b value_welltypedb vs (op_paramtypes op) = true →

value_welltyped (op_interp prec op vs) (op_resulttype op).

6.4 Well-typedness of values and evaluation

Lemma *expr_value_welltyped cls*:

In cls (prog_class prog) →
 $\forall e t,$
expr_welltyped value_welltypedb (cls_itfs cls) (Some cls) [] e t = true →
value_welltyped (eval_prog e) t.

Lemma *exprs_values_welltyped cls*:

In cls (prog_class prog) →
 $\forall es ts,$
forall2b (fun e t ⇒ expr_welltyped value_welltypedb (cls_itfs cls) (Some cls) [] e t) es ts
 $= true →$
forall2b value_welltypedb (map (eval_prog) es) ts = true.

Lemma *exprs_welltyped_list_consistent cls cls0 es ts*:

In cls (prog_class prog) →
In cls0 (prog_class prog) →
forall2b (expr_welltyped value_welltypedb (cls_itfs cls) (Some cls) []) es ts = true →
list_consistent cls0 (map (eval_prog) es) ts.

Lemma *field_values_welltyped_consistent cls fvs*:

In cls (prog_class prog) →
field_values_welltyped fvs (cls_fds cls) →
Forall2 (field_consistent cls) fvs (cls_fds cls).

Lemma *field_values_welltyped_field_names fdvs fds*:

field_values_welltyped fdvs fds →
fdvs = combine (map snd fds) (map snd fdvs).

Lemma *ghost_field_values_welltyped_consistent fvs fds gfvs gfs*:

field_values_welltyped fvs fds →
ghost_field_values_welltyped fvs gfvs gfs →
Forall2 (class_gf_consistent (fun e ⇒ eval pr (expr_subst (fun x ⇒ e_val (assoc v_unit
(combine (map snd fds) (map snd fvs)) x)) e))) gfvs gfs.

6.5 Well-typedness of values and substitution

Fixpoint *leave_vars(env: list (var × type))(f: var → expr): var → expr :=*

match env with
 $[] ⇒ f$
 $| (x, t)::env ⇒ leave_var x (leave_vars env f)$
end.

Lemma *In_leave_vars env f x*:

In x (map fst env) →

leave_vars env f x = e_var x.

Lemma *not_In_leave_vars env f x:*

*¬ In x (map fst env) →
leave_vars env f x = f x.*

Lemma *expr_welltyped_subst itfs cls env xs vs e t:*

*forall2b value_welltypedb vs (map fst xs) = true →
expr_welltyped (fun _ _ ⇒ false) itfs cls (env ++ map (fun tx ⇒ (snd tx, fst tx)) xs) e
t = true →
expr_welltyped value_welltypedb itfs cls env (expr_subst (leave_vars env (fun x ⇒ e_val
(assoc v_unit (combine (map snd xs) vs) x))) e) t = true.*

Lemma *expr_welltyped_subst0 itfs cls env xs vs e t:*

*forall2b value_welltypedb vs (map fst xs) = true →
expr_welltyped value_welltypedb itfs cls (env ++ map (fun tx ⇒ (snd tx, fst tx)) xs) e t
= true →
expr_welltyped value_welltypedb itfs cls env (expr_subst (leave_vars env (fun x ⇒ e_val
(assoc v_unit (combine (map snd xs) vs) x))) e) t = true.*

Lemma *exprs_welltyped_subst itfs cls xs vs env es ts:*

*forall2b value_welltypedb vs (map fst xs) = true →
forall2b (expr_welltyped (fun _ _ ⇒ false) itfs cls (env ++ map (fun tx ⇒ (snd tx, fst
tx)) xs)) es ts = true →
forall2b (expr_welltyped value_welltypedb itfs cls env) (map (expr_subst (leave_vars env
(fun x ⇒ e_val (assoc v_unit (combine (map snd xs) vs) x)))) es) ts = true.*

Lemma *exprs_welltyped_subst0 itfs cls xs vs env es ts:*

*forall2b value_welltypedb vs (map fst xs) = true →
forall2b (expr_welltyped value_welltypedb itfs cls (env ++ map (fun tx ⇒ (snd tx, fst tx))
xs)) es ts = true →
forall2b (expr_welltyped value_welltypedb itfs cls env) (map (expr_subst (leave_vars env
(fun x ⇒ e_val (assoc v_unit (combine (map snd xs) vs) x)))) es) ts = true.*

Lemma *cmd_welltyped_subst cls xs vs env c t:*

*forall2b value_welltypedb vs (map fst xs) = true →
cmd_welltyped (fun _ _ ⇒ false) cls (env ++ map (fun tx ⇒ (snd tx, fst tx)) xs) c t =
true →
cmd_welltyped value_welltypedb cls env (cmd_subst (leave_vars env (fun x ⇒ e_val (assoc
v_unit (combine (map snd xs) vs) x))) c) t = true.*

Lemma *cmd_welltyped_subst0 cls xs vs env c t:*

*forall2b value_welltypedb vs (map fst xs) = true →
cmd_welltyped value_welltypedb cls (env ++ map (fun tx ⇒ (snd tx, fst tx)) xs) c t =
true →
cmd_welltyped value_welltypedb cls env (cmd_subst (leave_vars env (fun x ⇒ e_val (assoc
v_unit (combine (map snd xs) vs) x))) c) t = true.*

6.6 Further properties of well-typedness of values

Lemma *exprs_welltyped_field_values_welltyped cls es fds*:

*In cls (prog_clss prog) →
forall2b (expr_welltyped value_welltypedb (cls_itfs cls) (Some cls) []) es (map fst fds) =
true →
field_values_welltyped (combine (map snd fds) (map (eval_ prog) es)) fds.*

Definition *gfenv cls := map (fun fd ⇒ (snd fd, fst fd)) (cls_fds cls).*

Lemma *In_cls_prog_ghost_fields_welltyped cls*:

*In cls (prog_clss prog) →
forallb (fun gf ⇒ match gf with GField (GFSpec t g) e ⇒ expr_welltyped (fun _ ⇒
false) (cls_itfs cls) None (gfenv cls) e t end) (cls_gfs cls) = true.*

Lemma *expr_welltyped_None_Some_cls cls env*:

$\forall e t,$
*expr_welltyped (fun _ ⇒ false) (cls_itfs cls) None env e t = true →
expr_welltyped (fun _ ⇒ false) (cls_itfs cls) (Some cls) env e t = true.*

Lemma *ghost_field_values_welltyped_lemma cls es gfs*:

*In cls (prog_clss prog) →
forall2b value_welltypedb (map (eval_ prog) es) (map fst (cls_fds cls)) = true →
forallb (fun gf ⇒ match gf with GField (GFSpec t g) e ⇒ expr_welltyped (fun _ ⇒
false) (cls_itfs cls) None (gfenv cls) e t end) gfs = true →
ghost_field_values_welltyped (combine (map snd (cls_fds cls)) (map (eval_ prog) es))
(map (fun gf ⇒ match gf with GField (GFSpec _ g) e ⇒ (g, eval_ prog (expr_subst
(fun x ⇒ e_val (assoc v_unit (combine (map snd (cls_fds cls)) (map (eval_ prog) es)) x))
e)) end) gfs) gfs.*

6.7 Well-foundedness of the program method precedence relation

Definition *class_rank(C: cname): nat := index_of (map clsname (prog_clss prog)) C.*

Lemma *class_rank_of_import_lt_lemma itfs k class css*:

*(distinct (map clsname class) = true) →
($\forall cls, In cls class \rightarrow class_rank (clsname cls) = k + index_of (map clsname class) (clsname$
 $cls)$) →
($\forall cs, In cs css \rightarrow class_rank (clsname cs) < k$) →
*class_imports_sat itfs css class = true →
($\forall cls, In cls class \rightarrow \forall cs, In cs (cls_cspecs cls) \rightarrow class_rank (clsname cs) < class_rank$
 $(clsname cls)$).**

Lemma *class_rank_of_import_lt cls cs*:

In cls (prog_cls prog) →
In cs (cls_cspects cls) →
class_rank (csname cs) < class_rank (clsname cls).

Definition *method_rank C m :=*
match lookup_class (prog_cls prog) C with
None ⇒ 0
| Some cls ⇒ index_of (map m_name (clsmeths cls)) m
end.

Lemma *list_prec_index_of {A} {eqa: EqDec A} (xs: list A) (x y: A):*
distinct xs = true →
list_prec xs x y = true →
index_of xs x < index_of xs y.

Lemma *prog_clsprec_iter_rank n C1 C2:*
prog_clsprec_iter n (prog_cls prog) C1 C2 = true →
class_rank C1 < class_rank C2.

Lemma *wf_pr_lemma:*
∀ rC,
Acc lt rC →
∀ rm,
Acc lt rm →
∀ C m,
class_rank C = rC →
method_rank C m = rm →
Acc pr (C, m).

Lemma *wf_pr: well_founded pr.*

6.8 Class precedence implies program precedence

Lemma *class_prec_implies_prog_prec cls:*
In cls (prog_cls prog) → ∀ Cm1 Cm2, class_prec cls Cm1 Cm2 = true → pr Cm1 Cm2.

6.9 Well-typedness of expressions and commands and subtyping

Lemma *is_subtype_trans t2 t1 t0:*
is_subtype t2 t1 = true →
is_subtype t1 t0 = true →
is_subtype t2 t0 = true.

Lemma *expr_welltyped_subtype value_welltypedb itfs cls env e t1 t0:*

$(\forall v t1 t0, is_subtype t1 t0 = true \rightarrow value_welltypedb v t1 = true \rightarrow value_welltypedb v t0 = true) \rightarrow$
 $is_subtype t1 t0 = true \rightarrow$
 $expr_welltyped value_welltypedb itfs cls env e t1 = true \rightarrow$
 $expr_welltyped value_welltypedb itfs cls env e t0 = true.$

Lemma *cmd_welltyped_subtype* *cls env c t1 t0*:

$is_subtype t1 t0 = true \rightarrow$
 $cmd_welltyped (\text{fun } - \Rightarrow \text{false}) cls env c t1 = true \rightarrow$
 $cmd_welltyped (\text{fun } - \Rightarrow \text{false}) cls env c t0 = true.$

6.10 Weakening the value well-typedness predicate in expression and command well-typedness

Lemma *expr_welltyped_weaken value_welltypedb0 value_welltypedb1 itfs cls env*:

$(\forall v t, value_welltypedb0 v t = true \rightarrow value_welltypedb1 v t = true) \rightarrow$
 $\forall e t,$
 $expr_welltyped value_welltypedb0 itfs cls env e t = true \rightarrow$
 $expr_welltyped value_welltypedb1 itfs cls env e t = true.$

Lemma *exprs_welltyped_weaken value_welltypedb0 value_welltypedb1 itfs cls env*:

$(\forall v t, value_welltypedb0 v t = true \rightarrow value_welltypedb1 v t = true) \rightarrow$
 $\forall es ts,$
 $forall2b (expr_welltyped value_welltypedb0 itfs cls env) es ts = true \rightarrow$
 $forall2b (expr_welltyped value_welltypedb1 itfs cls env) es ts = true.$

Lemma *cmd_welltyped_weaken value_welltypedb0 value_welltypedb1 cls env c t*:

$(\forall v t, value_welltypedb0 v t = true \rightarrow value_welltypedb1 v t = true) \rightarrow$
 $cmd_welltyped value_welltypedb0 cls env c t = true \rightarrow$
 $cmd_welltyped value_welltypedb1 cls env c t = true.$

6.11 Soundness of command correctness

Inductive *Qsat*: *outcome* \rightarrow *type* \rightarrow (*value* \rightarrow **Prop**) \rightarrow **Prop** :=

| *Qsat_terminates* *v t (Q: value* \rightarrow **Prop**):

$value_welltyped v t \rightarrow$
 $Q v \rightarrow$
 $Qsat (\text{terminates } v) t Q.$

Lemma *soundness_lemma*:

$\forall l,$
 $Acc (\text{level_lt } pr) l \rightarrow$
 $\forall cls,$

In cls (prog_class prog) →
∀ c Q,
correct cls pr l c Q →
∀ t O,
cmd_welltyped value_welltypedb cls [] c t = true →
exec prog c O →
Qsat O t Q.

Theorem *soundness cls l c t Q:*

In cls (prog_class prog) →
cmd_welltyped (fun _ _ ⇒ false) cls [] c t = true →
correct cls pr l c Q →
¬ exec prog c diverges.

End Prog.

End Soundness.

Chapter 7

Library NonWf

Require Import *ClassicalDescription*.

Require Import *Epsilon*.

Section *NonWf*.

Variable *A*: Type.

Variable *lt*: $A \rightarrow A \rightarrow \text{Prop}$.

CoInductive *descending_chain*: $A \rightarrow \text{Type} :=$

| *dc_cons* *a0* *a*:

lt *a0* *a* \rightarrow

descending_chain *a0* \rightarrow

descending_chain *a*

.

Definition *nonwf_dc*: $\forall a, \neg \text{Acc } lt \ a \rightarrow \text{descending_chain } a$.

Defined.

Inductive *dc_mem*: $\forall \{a\} (c: \text{descending_chain } a), A \rightarrow \text{Prop} :=$

| *dc_mem_head* *a0* *a* *H* *c0*:

dc_mem (*dc_cons* *a0* *a* *H* *c0*) *a*

| *dc_mem_tail* *a0* *a* *H* *c0* *a'*:

dc_mem *c0* *a'* \rightarrow

dc_mem (*dc_cons* *a0* *a* *H* *c0*) *a'*

.

Lemma *dc_nonwf*:

$\forall \{a\} (c: \text{descending_chain } a) \ a'$,

dc_mem *c* *a'* $\rightarrow \exists \ a'', \text{dc_mem } c \ a'' \wedge lt \ a'' \ a'$.

End *NonWf*.

Chapter 8

Library WellOrderingTheoremEx

By Bart Jacobs. Based on *Gert Smolka, Zermelo's Well-Ordering Theorem for Type Theory, Lecture Notes, 2015*. Itself based on Zermelo's 1908 proof.

I extended Smolka's proof straightforwardly to prove that any well-founded relation can be extended to a well-ordering.

Section *Lt0*.

Variable *A*: Type.

Variable *lt0*: $A \rightarrow A \rightarrow \text{Prop}$.

Hypothesis *wf_lt0*: *well_founded lt0*.

Lemma *lt0_irrefl* *x*: $\neg \text{lt0 } x \ x$.

Definition *le*(*x y*: *A*): Prop.

Defined.

Lemma *le_refl* *x*: *le* *x* *x*.

Lemma *le_trans* *x y z*: *le* *x* *y* \rightarrow *le* *y* *z* \rightarrow *le* *x* *z*.

Theorem *le_linear* *x y*: *le* *x* *y* \vee *le* *y* *x*.

Definition *lt* *a a'* := *le* *a* *a'* \wedge \neg *le* *a'* *a*.

Lemma *wf*: *well_founded lt*.

Lemma *le_eq_or_lt* *a a'*: *le* *a* *a'* \rightarrow *a* = *a'* \vee *lt* *a* *a'*.

Lemma *le_antisym* *a a'*: *le* *a* *a'* \rightarrow *le* *a'* *a* \rightarrow *a* = *a'*.

Lemma *le_lt_trans* *a1 a2 a3*: *le* *a1* *a2* \rightarrow *lt* *a2* *a3* \rightarrow *lt* *a1* *a3*.

Lemma *lt_le_trans* *a1 a2 a3*: *lt* *a1* *a2* \rightarrow *le* *a2* *a3* \rightarrow *lt* *a1* *a3*.

Lemma *lt_trans* *a1 a2 a3*: *lt* *a1* *a2* \rightarrow *lt* *a2* *a3* \rightarrow *lt* *a1* *a3*.

Lemma *trichotomy* *a a'*: *lt* *a* *a'* \vee *a* = *a'* \vee *lt* *a'* *a*.

Lemma *lt_or_le* *x y*: *lt* *x* *y* \vee *le* *y* *x*.

Lemma *lt0_le x y*: $lt0\ x\ y \rightarrow le\ x\ y$.

Lemma *lt0_lt x y*: $lt0\ x\ y \rightarrow lt\ x\ y$.

End *Lt0*.

Chapter 9

Library MultisetOrder

```
Require Import ClassicalEpsilon.
Require Import FunctionalExtensionality.
Require Import Omega.
Require Wf_nat.
Require WellOrderingTheoremEx.

Section X.

Variable X: Type.
```

9.1 Multiplicity functions

```
Definition multfunc := X → nat.
Definition MFin x (M: multfunc) := M x ≠ 0.
Definition MFempty: multfunc := fun _ => 0.
Definition MFSing: X → multfunc := fun x y => if excluded_middle_informative (x = y) then 1 else 0.
Definition MFplus(M M': multfunc): multfunc := fun x => M x + M' x.
Definition MFinsert x M := MFplus M (MFSing x).
Definition MFrestrict P (M: multfunc) := fun x => if excluded_middle_informative (P x) then M x else 0.
Definition MFint (A B: multfunc) := fun x => min (A x) (B x).
Definition MFdiff (A B: multfunc) := fun x => A x - B x.

Lemma multfunc_extensionality (M M': multfunc): (∀ x, M x = M' x) → M = M'.
Lemma MFplus_commut(M1 M2: multfunc): MFplus M1 M2 = MFplus M2 M1.
Lemma MFplus_MFempty_l (M: multfunc): MFplus MFempty M = M.
Lemma MFplus_assoc M1 M2 M3: MFplus (MFplus M1 M2) M3 = MFplus M1 (MFplus M2 M3).
Lemma MFrestrict_MFempty P: MFrestrict P MFempty = MFempty.
```

Lemma *MFrestrict_MFinsert_True* ($P: X \rightarrow \text{Prop}$) $x M: P x \rightarrow MFrestrict P (MFinsert x M) = MFinsert x (MFrestrict P M)$.

Lemma *MFrestrict_MFinsert_False* ($P: X \rightarrow \text{Prop}$) $x M: \neg P x \rightarrow MFrestrict P (MFinsert x M) = MFrestrict P M$.

Lemma *MFin_MFplus* $x M M': MFin x (MFplus M M') \leftrightarrow MFin x M \vee MFin x M'$.

Lemma *MFin_MFsing* $x y: MFin x (MFsing y) \leftrightarrow x = y$.

Lemma *MFin_MFinsert* $x y M: MFin x (MFinsert y M) \leftrightarrow x = y \vee MFin x M$.

Lemma *MFint_MFempty* $M: MFint MFempty M = MFempty$.

Lemma *MFint_MFinsert_lt* $x A B: A x < B x \rightarrow MFint (MFinsert x A) B = MFinsert x (MFint A B)$.

Lemma *MFint_MFinsert_nlt* $x A B: \neg A x < B x \rightarrow MFint (MFinsert x A) B = MFint A B$.

Lemma *MFdiff_eq_MFint_MFdiff* $A B: MFdiff A B = MFint A (MFdiff A B)$.

Lemma *MFint_commut* $A B: MFint A B = MFint B A$.

9.2 is_multiset

Inductive *is_multiset*: *multifunc* \rightarrow *Prop* :=

| *is_multiset_empty*: *is_multiset* *MFempty*

| *is_multiset_insert* $x M$:

is_multiset $M \rightarrow$

is_multiset (*MFinsert* $x M$)

.

Lemma *is_multiset_MFrestrict* $P M: is_multiset M \rightarrow is_multiset (MFrestrict P M)$.

Lemma *is_multiset_MFint* $A B: is_multiset A \rightarrow is_multiset (MFint A B)$.

9.3 Multisets

Definition *multiset* := $\{M : multifunc \mid is_multiset M\}$.

Definition *Mmult*($M: multiset$)($x: X$): *nat* := *proj1_sig* $M x$.

Definition *Mempty*: *multiset*.

Defined.

Definition *Msing*($x: X$): *multiset*.

Defined.

Definition *Mplus*($M M': multiset$): *multiset*.

Defined.

Definition *Mrestrict* ($P: X \rightarrow \mathbf{Prop}$) ($M: \text{multiset}$): *multiset*.

Defined.

Definition *Minsert*($x: X$)($M: \text{multiset}$): *multiset* := *Mplus* M (*Msing* x).

Definition *Min*($x: X$)($M: \text{multiset}$): \mathbf{Prop} := *Mmult* M $x \neq 0$.

Definition *Mint* ($A B: \text{multiset}$): *multiset*.

Defined.

Definition *Mdiff* ($A B: \text{multiset}$): *multiset*.

Defined.

Lemma *M_ext* ($M M': \text{multiset}$): $(\forall x, \text{Mmult } M \ x = \text{Mmult } M' \ x) \rightarrow M = M'$.

Lemma *Mrestrict_True* ($P: X \rightarrow \mathbf{Prop}$) $M \ x: P \ x \rightarrow \text{Mmult } (\text{Mrestrict } P \ M) \ x = \text{Mmult } M \ x$.

Lemma *Mrestrict_False* ($P: X \rightarrow \mathbf{Prop}$) $M \ x: \neg P \ x \rightarrow \text{Mmult } (\text{Mrestrict } P \ M) \ x = 0$.

Lemma *Mmult_Mempty* $x: \text{Mmult } \text{Mempty} \ x = 0$.

Lemma *Mmult_Mplus* $M M' \ x: \text{Mmult } (\text{Mplus } M \ M') \ x = \text{Mmult } M \ x + \text{Mmult } M' \ x$.

Lemma *Mplus_Mempty* $M M': \text{Mplus } M \ M' = \text{Mempty} \rightarrow M = \text{Mempty} \wedge M' = \text{Mempty}$.

Lemma *Min_Mempty* $x: \neg \text{Min } x \ \text{Mempty}$.

Lemma *Min_Mrestrict* $x \ P \ M: \text{Min } x \ (\text{Mrestrict } P \ M) \leftrightarrow P \ x \wedge \text{Min } x \ M$.

Lemma *Mmult_Mint* $A \ B \ x: \text{Mmult } (\text{Mint } A \ B) \ x = \text{min } (\text{Mmult } A \ x) \ (\text{Mmult } B \ x)$.

Lemma *Mmult_Mdiff* $A \ B \ x: \text{Mmult } (\text{Mdiff } A \ B) \ x = \text{Mmult } A \ x - \text{Mmult } B \ x$.

Lemma *Mint_commut* $A \ B: \text{Mint } A \ B = \text{Mint } B \ A$.

Lemma *Mplus_Mint_Mdiff* $A \ B: A = \text{Mplus } (\text{Mint } A \ B) \ (\text{Mdiff } A \ B)$.

9.4 Multiset order

Variable *lt*: $X \rightarrow X \rightarrow \mathbf{Prop}$.

Definition *le* $x \ y := x = y \vee \text{lt } x \ y$.

Definition *Mle* $A \ B :=$

$\exists M \ A' \ B', A = \text{Mplus } M \ A' \wedge B = \text{Mplus } M \ B' \wedge \forall x, \text{Min } x \ A' \rightarrow \exists y, \text{Min } y \ B' \wedge \text{lt } x \ y$.

Definition *Mlt* $A \ B := \text{Mle } A \ B \wedge A \neq B$.

Definition *lt_ex* := *WellOrderingTheoremEx.lt* _ *lt*.

Definition *le_ex* := *WellOrderingTheoremEx.le* _ *lt*.

Lemma *le_ex_linear* $x \ y: \text{le_ex } x \ y \vee \text{le_ex } y \ x$.

Lemma *is_multiset_max_ex* $M: \text{is_multiset } M \rightarrow M = \text{MFinempty} \vee \exists x, \text{MFin } x \ M \wedge \forall y, \text{MFin } y \ M \rightarrow \text{le_ex } y \ x$.

Lemma *M_max_ex* $M: M = \text{Mempty} \vee \exists x, \text{Min } x \ M \wedge \forall y, \text{Min } y \ M \rightarrow \text{le_ex } y \ x$.

9.5 Well-foundedness of multiset order

Variable *wf_lt*: *well_founded lt*.

Lemma *lt_irrefl* *x*: $\neg lt\ x\ x$.

Definition *Mlt_ex_at* *b A B* :=

$Mmult\ A\ b < Mmult\ B\ b$
 $\wedge (\forall x, lt_ex\ b\ x \rightarrow Mmult\ A\ x = Mmult\ B\ x)$.

Definition *Mlt_ex* *A B* := $\exists b, Mlt_ex_at\ b\ A\ B$.

Lemma *Mlt_implies_Mlt_ex* *A B*: $Mlt\ A\ B \rightarrow Mlt_ex\ A\ B$.

Lemma *wf_Mlt_ex0*:

$\forall x, Acc\ lt_ex\ x \rightarrow$
 $\forall n, Acc\ Peano.lt\ n \rightarrow$
 $\forall M,$
 $(\forall b, lt_ex\ x\ b \rightarrow \forall M', Mlt_ex_at\ b\ M'\ M \rightarrow Acc\ Mlt_ex\ M') \rightarrow$
 $Mmult\ M\ x \leq n \rightarrow$
 $Acc\ Mlt_ex\ M$.

Lemma *wf_Mlt_ex*: *well_founded Mlt_ex*.

Theorem *wf_Mlt*: *well_founded Mlt*.

9.6 Transitivity of multiset order

Hypothesis *lt_trans*: $\forall x\ y\ z, lt\ x\ y \rightarrow lt\ y\ z \rightarrow lt\ x\ z$.

Lemma *lt_le_trans* *x y z*: $lt\ x\ y \rightarrow le\ y\ z \rightarrow lt\ x\ z$.

Lemma *le_lt_trans* *x y z*: $le\ x\ y \rightarrow lt\ y\ z \rightarrow lt\ x\ z$.

Lemma *le_trans* *x y z*: $le\ x\ y \rightarrow le\ y\ z \rightarrow le\ x\ z$.

Definition *Mle'* *A B* := $\forall x, Mmult\ B\ x < Mmult\ A\ x \rightarrow \exists y, lt\ x\ y \wedge Mmult\ A\ y < Mmult\ B\ y$.

Lemma *is_multiset_maximal* *M*: $is_multiset\ M \rightarrow M = MEmpty \vee \exists x, MFin\ x\ M \wedge \forall y, MFin\ y\ M \rightarrow \neg lt\ x\ y$.

Lemma *M_maximal* *M*: $M = Mempty \vee \exists x, Min\ x\ M \wedge \forall y, Min\ y\ M \rightarrow \neg lt\ x\ y$.

Lemma *Mle_iff_Mle'* *A B*: $Mle\ A\ B \leftrightarrow Mle'\ A\ B$.

Lemma *Mle_trans* *A B C*: $Mle\ A\ B \rightarrow Mle\ B\ C \rightarrow Mle\ A\ C$.

Lemma *Mlt_antisym* *A B*: $Mlt\ A\ B \rightarrow Mlt\ B\ A \rightarrow False$.

Theorem *Mlt_trans* *A B C*: $Mlt\ A\ B \rightarrow Mlt\ B\ C \rightarrow Mlt\ A\ C$.

End X.

Chapter 10

Library SpecStyle

Require Export *Util*.

Require Export *Programs*.

Require Export *MultisetOrder*.

Definition *mbag* := *multiset mname*.

Definition *mbag_lt*(*pr*: *prec*)(*M1 M2*: *mbag*): Prop :=
 Mlt _ (WellOrderingTheoremEx.lt _ pr) M1 M2.

Lemma *wf_mbag_lt pr*: *well_founded pr* → *well_founded (mbag_lt pr)*.

Module *SpecStyleTypes* <: *OTHER_TYPES*.

 Inductive *other_type_* := *ot_num* | *ot_mname* | *ot_mbag*.

 Definition *other_type* := *other_type_*.

 Definition *other_type_eq_dec* (*ot1 ot2*: *other_type*): {*ot1 = ot2*} + {*ot1 ≠ ot2*}.
 Defined.

 Inductive *other_value_* :=
 | *ov_num*(*n*: *nat*)
 | *ov_mname*(*Cm*: *mname*)
 | *ov_mbag*(*M*: *mbag*).

 Definition *other_value* := *other_value_*.

 Inductive *other_value_welltyped_*: *other_value* → *other_type* → Prop :=
 | *num_welltyped n*:
 other_value_welltyped_ (ov_num n) ot_num
 | *mname_welltyped Cm*:
 other_value_welltyped_ (ov_mname Cm) ot_mname
 | *mbag_welltyped M*:
 other_value_welltyped_ (ov_mbag M) ot_mbag
 .

 Definition *other_value_welltyped* := *other_value_welltyped_*.

End *SpecStyleTypes*.

Module *SpecStyleOperators* <: OPERATORS *SpecStyleTypes*.

Module Export *TheTypes* := Types *SpecStyleTypes*.

Definition *t_num* := *t_other ot_num*.

Definition *t_mname* := *t_other ot_mname*.

Definition *t_mbag* := *t_other ot_mbag*.

Notation *v_num n* := (*v_other (ov_num n)*).

Notation *v_mname Cm* := (*v_other (ov_mname Cm)*).

Notation *v_mbag M* := (*v_other (ov_mbag M)*).

Inductive *operator_* :=

op_boollit(*b*: bool)
| *op_numlit*(*n*: nat)
| *op_plus*
| *op_minus*
| *op_mname*(*Cm*: mname)
| *op_msing*
| *op_uplus*
| *op_mbag_lt*
.

Definition *operator* := *operator_*.

Definition *eq_dec_operator* (*op1 op2*: operator): {*op1 = op2*} + {*op1 ≠ op2*}.

Defined.

Fixpoint *op_paramtypes*(*op*: operator): list type :=

 match *op* with
 | *op_plus* | *op_minus* ⇒ [*t_num*, *t_num*]
 | *op_msing* ⇒ [*t_mname*]
 | *op_uplus* | *op_mbag_lt* ⇒ [*t_mbag*, *t_mbag*]
 | - ⇒ []
 end.

Fixpoint *op_resulttype*(*op*: operator): type :=

 match *op* with
 | *op_boollit* - | *op_mbag_lt* ⇒ *t_bool*
 | *op_numlit* - | *op_plus* | *op_minus* ⇒ *t_num*
 | *op_mname* *Cm* ⇒ *t_mname*
 | *op_msing* | *op_uplus* ⇒ *t_mbag*
 end.

Inductive *level_lt*(*pr*: prec): value → value → Prop :=

| *level_lt_intro* *M1 M2*:
 mbag_lt pr M1 M2 →
 level_lt pr (v_mbag M1) (v_mbag M2)

Definition *level_lt* := *level_lt_*.

Lemma *wf_level_lt* *pr*: *well_founded* *pr* → *well_founded* (*level_lt* *pr*).

Fixpoint *op_interp*(*pr*: *prec*)(*op*: *operator*)(*vs*: *list value*): *value* :=
 match *op*, *vs* with
 op_boollit *b*, _ ⇒ *v_bool* *b*
 | *op_numlit* *n*, _ ⇒ *v_num* *n*
 | *op_plus*, [*v_num* *n1*, *v_num* *n2*] ⇒ *v_num* (*n1* + *n2*)
 | *op_minus*, [*v_num* *n1*, *v_num* *n2*] ⇒ *v_num* (*n1* - *n2*)
 | *op_mname* *Cm*, _ ⇒ *v_mname* *Cm*
 | *op_msing*, [*v_mname* *Cm*] ⇒ *v_mbag* (*Msing* - *Cm*)
 | *op_uplus*, [*v_mbag* *M1*, *v_mbag* *M2*] ⇒ *v_mbag* (*Mplus* - *M1* *M2*)
 | *op_mbag_lt*, [*v_mbag* *M1*, *v_mbag* *M2*] ⇒ *v_bool* (*Trueb* (*mbag_lt* *pr* *M1* *M2*))
 | _, _ ⇒ *v_unit*
 end.

Lemma *op_interp_welltyped0*:

 ∀ *obj_welltyped* *pr* *op* *vs*,

 Forall2 (*value_welltyped0* *obj_welltyped*) *vs* (*op_paramtypes* *op*) →
 value_welltyped0 *obj_welltyped* (*op_interp* *pr* *op* *vs*) (*op_resulttype* *op*).

End *SpecStyleOperators*.

Require Export *Soundness*.

Include *Soundness.Soundness SpecStyleTypes SpecStyleOperators*.

Definition *e_true* := *e_op* (*op_boollit* *true*) [].

Definition *e_num* *n* := *e_op* (*op_numlit* *n*) [].

Definition *e_plus* *e1* *e2* := *e_op* *op_plus* [*e1*, *e2*].

Definition *e_minus* *e1* *e2* := *e_op* *op_minus* [*e1*, *e2*].

Definition *e_msing* *Cm* := *e_op* *op_msing* [*e_op* (*op_mname* *Cm*) []].

Definition *e_uplus* *e1* *e2* := *e_op* *op_uplus* [*e1*, *e2*].

Definition *e_mcons* *Cm* *e* := *e_uplus* (*e_msing* *Cm*) *e*.

Definition *e_mbag_lt* *e1* *e2* := *e_op* *op_mbag_lt* [*e1*, *e2*].

Chapter 11

Library MethodBagLemmas

Require Import *Classical*.

Require Export *SpecStyle*.

Lemma *Mplus_Mempty_l* X (M : *multiset* X): $Mplus$ $Mempty$ $M = M$.

Lemma *Mplus_commut* X ($M1$ $M2$: *multiset* X):

$Mplus$ $M1$ $M2 = Mplus$ $M2$ $M1$.

Require Import *Omega*.

Lemma *Mplus_Mempty_r* X (M : *multiset* X): $Mplus$ M $Mempty = M$.

Lemma *Mmult_Msing_eq* X (x : X):

$Mmult$ ($Msing$ x) $x = 1$.

Lemma *Mmult_Msing_neq* X (x y : X):

$x \neq y \rightarrow$

$Mmult$ ($Msing$ x) $y = 0$.

Lemma *mbag_lt_Mplus_Msing_r* pr M Cm : $mbag_lt$ pr M ($Mplus$ ($Msing$ Cm) M).

Lemma *mbag_lt_Mplus_Msing_l* pr M Cm : $mbag_lt$ pr M ($Mplus$ M ($Msing$ Cm)).

Lemma *Min_Msing* X (x y : X):

Min x ($Msing$ y) \leftrightarrow

$x = y$.

Lemma *mbag_lt_Msing_prec* (pr : *prec*) $Cm1$ $Cm2$: *well_founded* $pr \rightarrow pr$ $Cm1$ $Cm2 \rightarrow$
 $mbag_lt$ pr ($Msing$ $Cm1$) ($Msing$ $Cm2$).

Lemma *Mplus_assoc* X ($M1$ $M2$ $M3$: *multiset* X): $Mplus$ ($Mplus$ $M1$ $M2$) $M3 = Mplus$ $M1$
($Mplus$ $M2$ $M3$).

Lemma *Mplus_mono_r* pr $M1$ $M2$ M :

$mbag_lt$ pr $M1$ $M2 \rightarrow$

$mbag_lt$ pr ($Mplus$ M $M1$) ($Mplus$ M $M2$).

Lemma *Mplus_mono_l* pr M $M1$ $M2$:

$mbag_lt$ pr $M1$ $M2 \rightarrow$

$mbag_lt\ pr\ (Mplus\ M1\ M)\ (Mplus\ M2\ M).$

Lemma $mbag_lt_Mplus_Msing_prec\ pr\ Cm1\ Cm2\ M:$
 $well_founded\ pr\ \rightarrow$
 $(pr\ Cm1\ Cm2: Prop)\ \rightarrow$
 $mbag_lt\ pr\ (Mplus\ (Msing\ Cm1)\ M)\ (Mplus\ (Msing\ Cm2)\ M).$

Lemma $mbag_lt_trans\ pr\ M1\ M2\ M3:$
 $well_founded\ pr\ \rightarrow$
 $mbag_lt\ pr\ M1\ M2\ \rightarrow$
 $mbag_lt\ pr\ M2\ M3\ \rightarrow$
 $mbag_lt\ pr\ M1\ M3.$

Lemma $M_eq_Mmult\ X\ (M1\ M2: multiset\ X)\ x: M1 = M2\ \rightarrow\ Mmult\ M1\ x = Mmult\ M2\ x.$

Lemma $mbag_lt_Msing\ pr\ M\ x:$
 $well_founded\ pr\ \rightarrow$
 $mbag_lt\ pr\ M\ (Msing\ x)\ \leftrightarrow$
 $\forall\ y,\ Min\ y\ M\ \rightarrow\ WellOrderingTheoremEx.lt_pr\ y\ x.$

Lemma $Min_Mplus\ X\ (x: X)\ M1\ M2:$
 $Min\ x\ (Mplus\ M1\ M2)\ \leftrightarrow$
 $Min\ x\ M1\ \vee\ Min\ x\ M2.$

Lemma $mbag_lt_Mplus_Msing\ pr\ M1\ M2\ Cm:$
 $well_founded\ pr\ \rightarrow$
 $mbag_lt\ pr\ M1\ (Msing\ Cm)\ \rightarrow$
 $mbag_lt\ pr\ M2\ (Msing\ Cm)\ \rightarrow$
 $mbag_lt\ pr\ (Mplus\ M1\ M2)\ (Msing\ Cm).$

Opaque $Msing\ Mplus.$

Chapter 12

Library Loopy

Require Export *SpecStyle*.

12.1 Interface Empty

```
interface Empty {}
```

Definition *Empty* := *Itf* "Empty" [] [].

12.2 Interface Func

```
interface Func {  
  ghost_field MethodBag applyLevel  
  num apply(num x)  
  req true  
  level this.applyLevel  
  ens true  
}
```

Definition *applyLevelSpec* := *GFSpec* *t_mbag* "applyLevel".

Definition *applySpec* :=

```
MSpec Instance t_num "apply" [(t_num, "x")]  
  e_true  
  (e_gfd (e_var "this") "Func" "applyLevel")  
  e_true.
```

Definition *Func* := *Itf* "Func" [*applyLevelSpec*] [*applySpec*].

12.3 Class Util

```
class Util imports Empty, Func implements Empty {
  static num deriv(Func f, num x)
    req true
    level {|Util.deriv|} + f.applyLevel
    ens true
  {
    num tmp1 := f.apply(x + 1);
    num tmp2 := f.apply(x);
    tmp1 - tmp2
  }
}
```

Definition *derivSpec* :=

```
MSpec Static t_num "deriv" [(t_in "Func", "f"), (t_num, "x")]
  e_true
  (e_mcons ("Util", "deriv") (e_gfd (e_var "f") "Func" "applyLevel"))
  e_true.
```

Definition *Util* :=

```
Class "Util" [| [Empty, Func] [| "Empty" [| [
  Meth derivSpec
  (c_let
    t_num "tmp1" (c_icall (e_var "f") "Func" "apply" [e_plus (e_var "x") (e_num
1)])
  (c_let
    t_num "tmp2" (c_icall (e_var "f") "Func" "apply" [e_var "x"])
    (c_expr (e_minus (e_var "tmp1") (e_var "tmp2"))))]
  ].
```

12.4 Class Loopy

```
class Loopy imports Func, Util implements Func {
  ghost_field MethodBag applyLevel = {|Loopy.apply|}
  num apply(num x) { Util.deriv(this, x) }
  static num main()
    req true
    level {|Loopy.main|}
    ens true
  {
    Func f := new Loopy();
    Util.deriv(f, 0)
  }
```

```

    }
}

```

Definition *Loopy* :=

```

Class "Loopy" [] [Func] [spec Util] "Func" [
  GField applyLevelSpec (e_msing ("Loopy", "apply"))
] [
  Meth applySpec
    (c_scall "Util" "deriv" [e_var "this", e_var "x"]),
  Meth
    (MSpec Static t_num "main" []
      e_true
      (e_msing ("Loopy", "main"))
      e_true)
    (c_let
      (t_in "Func") "f" (c_new "Loopy" [])
      (c_scall "Util" "deriv" [e_var "f", e_num 0]))
].

```

12.5 The program

Definition *the_program* :=

```

Program [Empty, Func] [Util, Loopy].

```

Chapter 13

Library PlusOneFunc

Require Export *SpecStyle*.

13.1 Interface Empty

```
interface Empty {}
```

Definition *Empty* := *Itf* "Empty" [] [].

13.2 Interface Func

```
interface Func {  
  ghost_field MethodBag applyLevel  
  num apply(num x)  
  req true  
  level this.applyLevel  
  ens true  
}
```

Definition *applyLevelSpec* := *GFSpec* *t_mbag* "applyLevel".

Definition *applySpec* :=

```
MSpec Instance t_num "apply" [(t_num, "x")]  
  e_true  
  (e_gfd (e_var "this") "Func" "applyLevel")  
  e_true.
```

Definition *Func* := *Itf* "Func" [*applyLevelSpec*] [*applySpec*].

13.3 Class Util

```
class Util imports Empty, Func implements Empty {
  static num deriv(Func f, num x)
    req true
    level {|Util.deriv|} + f.applyLevel
    ens true
  {
    num tmp1 := f.apply(x + 1);
    num tmp2 := f.apply(x);
    tmp1 - tmp2
  }
}
```

Definition *derivSpec* :=

```
MSpec Static t_num "deriv" [(t_in "Func", "f"), (t_num, "x")]
  e_true
  (e_mcons ("Util", "deriv") (e_gfd (e_var "f") "Func" "applyLevel"))
  e_true.
```

Definition *Util* :=

```
Class "Util" [| [Empty, Func] [| "Empty" [| [
  Meth derivSpec
  (c_let
    t_num "tmp1" (c_icall (e_var "f") "Func" "apply" [e_plus (e_var "x") (e_num
1)])
  (c_let
    t_num "tmp2" (c_icall (e_var "f") "Func" "apply" [e_var "x"])
    (c_expr (e_minus (e_var "tmp1") (e_var "tmp2"))))]
].
```

13.4 Class ZeroFunc

```
class ZeroFunc imports Func implements Func {
  ghost_field num applyLevel = {|ZeroFunc.apply|}
  num apply(num x) { 0 }
  static Func create()
    req true
    level {|ZeroFunc.create|}
    ens result.applyLevel < {|ZeroFunc.create|}
  { new ZeroFunc() }
}
```

Definition *ZeroFunc* :=

```

Class "ZeroFunc" [] [Func] [] "Func" [
  GField applyLevelSpec (e_msing ("ZeroFunc", "apply"))
] [
  Meth applySpec (c_expr (e_num 0)),
  Meth
    (MSpec Static (t_in "Func") "create" []
      e_true
      (e_msing ("ZeroFunc", "create"))
      (e_mbag_lt (e_gfd (e_var "result") "Func" "applyLevel") (e_msing ("ZeroFunc",
"create")))))
    (c_new "ZeroFunc" [])
].

```

13.5 Class Plus1Func

```

class Plus1Func(Func f) imports Func implements Func {
  ghost_field num applyLevel = {|Plus1Func.apply|} + f.applyLevel
  num apply(num x) {
    num tmp1 := this.f.apply(x);
    tmp1 + 1
  }
  static Func create(Func f)
    req true
    level {|Plus1Func.create|} + f.applyLevel
    ens result.applyLevel < {|Plus1Func.create|} + f.applyLevel
    { new Plus1Func(f) }
}

```

Definition *Plus1Func* :=

```

Class "Plus1Func" [(t_in "Func", "f")] [Func] [] "Func" [
  GField applyLevelSpec (e_mcons ("Plus1Func", "apply") (e_gfd (e_var "f") "Func"
"applyLevel"))
] [
  Meth applySpec
    (c_let
      t_num "tmp1" (c_icall (e_fd (e_var "this") "f") "Func" "apply" [e_var "x"])
      (c_expr (e_plus (e_var "tmp1") (e_num 1))))),
  Meth
    (MSpec Static (t_in "Func") "create" [(t_in "Func", "f")]
      e_true
      (e_mcons ("Plus1Func", "create") (e_gfd (e_var "f") "Func" "applyLevel")))

```

```

      (e_mbag_lt (e_gfd (e_var "result") "Func" "applyLevel") (e_mcons ("Plus1Func",
"create") (e_gfd (e_var "f") "Func" "applyLevel"))))
      (c_new "Plus1Func" [e_var "f"])
    ].

```

13.6 Class Main

```

class Main imports Empty, Func, Util, ZeroFunc, Plus1Func implements Empty {
  static num main()
    req true
    level {|Main.main|}
    ens true
  {
    Func f1 := ZeroFunc.create();
    Func f2 := Plus1Func.create(f1);
    Func f3 := Plus1Func.create(f2);
    Util.deriv(f3, 0)
  }
}

```

Definition *Main* :=

```

Class "Main" [] [Empty, Func] [spec Util, spec ZeroFunc, spec Plus1Func] "Empty" [] [
  Meth
    (MSpec Static t_num "main" []
      e_true
      (e_msing ("Main", "main"))
      e_true)
  (c_let
    (t_in "Func") "f1" (c_scall "ZeroFunc" "create" []))
    (c_let
      (t_in "Func") "f2" (c_scall "Plus1Func" "create" [e_var "f1"])
      (c_let
        (t_in "Func") "f3" (c_scall "Plus1Func" "create" [e_var "f2"])
        (c_scall "Util" "deriv" [e_var "f3", e_num 0])))
  ].

```

13.7 The program

Definition *the_program* :=

```

Program [Empty, Func] [Util, ZeroFunc, Plus1Func, Main].

```

Chapter 14

Library ExamplesWellTyped

Require Export *SpecStyle*.

Require Import *PlusOneFunc*.

Lemma *Func_welltyped*: *itf_welltyped* *t_mbag* [*Func*] *Func* = *true*.

Lemma *Util_welltyped*: *cls_welltyped* *t_mbag* *Util* = *true*.

Lemma *ZeroFunc_welltyped*: *cls_welltyped* *t_mbag* *ZeroFunc* = *true*.

Lemma *Plus1Func_welltyped*: *cls_welltyped* *t_mbag* *Plus1Func* = *true*.

Lemma *Main_welltyped*: *cls_welltyped* *t_mbag* *Main* = *true*.

Lemma *PlusOneFunc_welltyped*: *program_welltyped* *t_mbag* *the_program*.

Require Import *Loopy*.

Lemma *Loopy_welltyped*: *program_welltyped* *t_mbag* *the_program*.

Chapter 15

Library ProgramExecutionTests

Require Export *SpecStyle*.

Opaque *Msing Mplus*.

15.1 A diverging execution

Require Import *Loopy*.

Lemma *loopy_loop*:

$\forall ef\ ex\ gfv,$

$eval_the_program\ ef = v_obj\ "Loopy"\ []\ "Func"\ [gfv] \rightarrow$
 $exec\ the_program\ (c_scall\ "Util"\ "deriv"\ [ef,\ ex])\ diverges.$

Goal $exec\ the_program\ (c_scall\ "Loopy"\ "main"\ [])\ diverges.$

15.2 A non-trivial terminating execution

Require Import *PlusOneFunc*.

Goal $exec\ the_program\ (c_scall\ "Main"\ "main"\ [])\ (terminates\ (v_num\ 0)).$

Chapter 16

Library PlusOneFunc_is_Correct

Require Export *PlusOneFunc*.

Require Export *MethodBagLemmas*.

Opaque *Msing Mplus*.

Theorem *Util_correct*: *class_correct Util*.

Theorem *ZeroFunc_correct*: *class_correct ZeroFunc*.

Theorem *Plus1Func_correct*: *class_correct Plus1Func*.

Theorem *Main_correct*: *class_correct Main*.

Theorem *PlusOneFunc_program_correct*: *program_correct the_program*.

Chapter 17

Library PlusOneFunc_terminates

Require Import *PlusOneFunc_is_Correct*.

Theorem *PlusOneFunc_always_terminates*: $\neg \text{exec } PlusOneFunc.the_program (c_scall "Main" "main" [])$ *diverges*.